

Ethnopharmacological Study: The Potential of Endemic Papuan Plants as Antioxidants

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ABSTRACT

Background: Indonesia is rich in biodiversity, particularly in terms of its flora. Papua is a region in eastern Indonesia; its climate and environment make it home to an abundance of endemic plants. The potential of these endemic plants for medicinal use has not yet been extensively studied.

Aims: The purpose of this study is to map the distribution of Papua's endemic plants with antioxidant potential, as well as their traditional uses.

Methodology: The methods used were a *narrative review* and a *literature review*.

Results: The results indicate that there are 32 areas in Papua with endemic plants rich in antioxidants, comprising 70 endemic plant species.

Conclusion: Papua is rich in antioxidants that have been utilised empirically by communities across various regions of Papua and by Papuan tribes

KEYWORDS: Antioxidants, Ethnopharmacology, Papua, Endemic plants

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
28 May 2026

Available on:
<https://ijpbms.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Antioxidants are compounds that donate one of their electrons to free radicals, thereby stabilising the free radicals(1). Antioxidants are molecules capable of inhibiting oxidation reactions; they are molecules that can donate one or more electrons to free radicals, thereby neutralising them. Based on their source, there are two types of antioxidants: natural antioxidants and synthetic antioxidants (2). According to the classification by Sen and Chakraborty (2011), antioxidants are divided into two categories: enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants. Enzymatic antioxidants constitute the primary defence system against oxidative stress(3). These enzymes are metalloproteins whose activity is highly dependent on the presence of metal ions and which function by preventing the formation of new free radical compounds.

Antioxidants are classified into six categories based on their source: Endogenous Antioxidants, such as bilirubin, glutathione, lipoic acid, NADH, NADPH, and enzymes (SOD, GR, GPx). Dietary Antioxidants, such as vitamin E, vitamin C, beta-carotene, xanthophylls, and polyphenols. Metal-Binding Proteins, e.g. albumin, metallothionein,

ferritin, transferrin. The classification of antioxidants based on their mechanism of action consists of three categories: Catalysts for neutralising ROS, e.g. SOD; CAT; GPx; Metal ion binding to prevent ROS production via the Haber-Weiss reaction, e.g. ferritin, ceruloplasmin, catechins. Antioxidant chain breaking, which destroys ROS, e.g. Vitamin C, Vitamin E, Glutathione, flavonoids. Plants generally possess antioxidant potential.

Specimen documentation is the primary evidence regarding knowledge of flora. It is therefore not surprising that publications on Papuan botany are very limited, let alone summary-type information. The literature, consisting mostly of technical articles, is scattered across various journals and books (written in various languages), or has limited circulation. There is no general guide such as the information available for Papua New Guinea (e.g., Borrell 1989, Conn 1995, Henty 1981, Johns 1987, 1988, 1989, Peekel 1984, Percival and Womersley 1975, Womersley 1978), although to a certain extent there are many similarities between the flora of Papua and that of PNG.

General reports are also very limited in number, consisting mainly of summaries of various expeditions (Archbold et al.

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1942, Brass 1941, Donnelly et al. 2004, Mack and Alonso 2000, Rand and Brass 1940, Ridley 1916, van Royen 1960, Takeuchi 2003b, Vink 1965, Wollaston 1914), botanical reviews (Conn 1994, Frodin 1988, 1990, Frodin and Gressitt 1982, Stevens 1989), plant lists (Coode et al. 1997, Sidiyasa et al. 1997, Streimann 1986), conservation studies (Craven and de Fretes 1987, Erftemeijer et al. 1989, Ruitenbeek 1992, Supriatna et al. 1999) and vegetation descriptions (van Balgooy 2001, Gibbs 1917, Hope 1976, Kalkman 1963, Mangen 1993, Rappard and van Royen 1959, van Royen 1956, 1963, 1965, 1967). Therefore, increased vegetation inventory and survey work in Papua will yield remarkable new findings, particularly regarding endemism, environmental quality and the biogeography of the flora.

Papua possesses several endemic species, although the collection is very limited. New Guinea has long been recognised as a centre of biodiversity, and the ongoing revision of Flora Malesiana (FM) supports this fact. Information to supplement the revision of the FM indicates that there are more endemic species in New Guinea than in any other region of Malesia; several taxa are concentrated in the northern part of the island (van Balgooy et al. 1996). Supriatna et al. (1999) estimated that endemism at the species level in Papua reaches 60–90%, and Johns (1995) estimated around 60–70% for the whole of New Guinea. Endemic plants with antioxidant potential have not been extensively studied, as reports on their distribution and empirical use have not been fully documented; hence, the research titled “Ethnopharmacological Study: The Potential of Papua’s Endemic Plants as Antioxidants” was conducted. This study aims to map the distribution of Papua’s endemic plants with antioxidant potential, as well as their empirical use.

METHODS

This study was conducted by reviewing several scientific articles that have been researched or published. The data obtained from this study utilised a narrative review method, drawing from databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, and ScienceDirect. The findings of this study were intended to identify several endemic plants of Papua with antioxidant potential that are still used by specific ethnic groups or communities. The review of the empirical use of endemic plants of Papua employed a literature review method by filtering accurate information from various sources in line with the research objectives. The distribution of endemic plants was mapped using GPS and visualised on a map.

RESULT DAN CONCLUSION

A. Distribution of Papuan Endemic Plants with Antioxidant Potential

The Papuan people consist of 254 ethnic groups inhabiting four ecological zones, namely: (1) the swamp, coastal and riverine zones; (2) the highland zone; (3) the foothill and small valley zones; and (4) the lowland, coastal

and island zones. The Papuan people are scattered across these four zones, so when developing policies for them, they cannot be treated uniformly as their cultural characteristics differ according to the zone in which they live(4).

Figure 1. Map of the Distribution of Medicinal Plants in Papua as Antioxidants

The research findings indicate that there are approximately 20 plant families used for medicinal purposes, namely *Plantaginaceae*, *Asteraceae*, *Crassulaceae*, *Zingiberaceae*, *Solanaceae*, *Lamiaceae*, *Apiaceae*, *Boraginaceae*, *Achantaceae*, *Cannaceae*, *Oxalidaceae*, *Campanulaceae*, *Selaginellaceae*, *Equisetaceae*, *Urticaceae*, *Rubiaceae*, *Nepenthaceae*, *Dipteridaceae*, and *Amaryllidaceae*. The parts of the plants utilised for medicinal purposes are the leaves, stems, flowers, rhizomes, and tubers(5).

The limited knowledge regarding plants in Papua indicates that many plant species remain undiscovered. Gaps in field exploration have been identified by Campbell (1989), Prance (1977), Stevens (1989) and Supriatna et al. (1999), so direct field studies in any location will yield new information. For example, a two-week survey along the coast near Kokas (Bomberai Peninsula) identified eight new plant taxa (Takeuchi 2003a) (Figure 3.1.1). Vegetation distribution maps (Middleton 1997, Pannell 1992) indicate uneven sampling. Given the limited botanical exploration in Papua, even surveys using brief study methods will yield highly valuable findings. The disparity in scientific information between Papua and PNG is reflected in local infrastructure conditions.

B. Empirical Use of Endemic Papuan Plants with Antioxidant Potential (Literature Review)

Papua is a fertile region, primarily due to its volcanic factors, high rainfall throughout the year, and dense tropical rainforest areas. This combination creates soil rich in biomass with an excellent natural nutrient cycle. It is highly likely that these plants are a source of antioxidants that has not yet been fully utilised. Several species of endemic Papuan plants are already known to possess antioxidant properties, as summarised in Table 1. Therefore, the conservation of these endemic species and further exploration of the antioxidant potential of other endemic Papuan plant species are of great importance.

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Table 1. List of endemic Papuan plants with antioxidant potential

No	Plant Name			Empirical Benefits	Antioxidant Test IC ₅₀	Potential Compounds	References
	Indonesia	Local (Papua)	Scientific				
1.	Lobi-Lobi (Jayapura)	Tomi-Tomi	<i>Flacourtia inermis</i> , <i>Roxb</i>	Reduces blood sugar levels, antihypertensive, and antioxidant.	67.6 µg/mL	Anthocyanins	(Fitriyani, 2018)(6)
2.	Betel leaf (all ethnic groups)	Forest betel	<i>Piper andacum L.</i>	Wound healing, stopping vomiting, reducing nausea, aiding digestion, as an antiseptic, killing bacteria, fungi and viruses.	47,252 µg/mL	Flavonoids, gallic tannins, steroids/triterpenoids, and phenols	(Hutan <i>et al.</i> , 2023)(7)
3.	Pekak (Papua New Guinea)	Star anise	<i>Illicium verum</i>	Antimicrobial, anticancer and antioxidant.	54,759 µg/mL	Essential oil, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, glycosides, and terpenes	(Putri <i>et al.</i> , 2021)(8)
4.	Kebar grass (Tambrau Regency)	Banondit	<i>Biophytum umbraculum Welw</i>	Used as a fertility remedy for women, to regulate menstruation, and to help increase sperm production.	27.74 µg/mL	Tannins, phenolic compounds, steroids, saponins, isoflavones, flavonoids, triterpenoids, alkaloids, steroids, glycosides.	(Widodo <i>et al.</i> , 2020) (9)
5.	Meniran (Sarmi)	Babiji Belakang	<i>Phyllanthus niruri L.</i>	For the treatment of kidney disorders and malaria.	17.64 µg/mL	Flavonoids, saponins, tannins (catechu and gallic), quinones, triterpenoids, coumarins and essential oils	(Marisi <i>et al.</i> , 2019) (10)
6.	Masoyi (Manokwari, Sorong, Nabire, Biak Numfor, Yapen, Waropen, Merauke, Jayapura)	Aikori	<i>Massoia aromatica Becc.</i>	As an antimicrobial, phagocytic, cytotoxic, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, antioxidant, analgesic agent, and for other effects via inhalation.	14.06 µg/mL	Flavonoids, phenols, alkaloids, steroids, triterpenoids, saponins, tannins, quinones, and coumarins.	Rosaria <i>et al.</i> , 2022)(11)
7.	Mulberry (Wamena)	Mulberry	<i>Morus rubra</i>	Used as a diuretic, fever remedy, a remedy for	12.6 µg/mL	Flavonoids, polyphenols and	(Pogaga <i>et al.</i> , 2020)(12)

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				malaria and high blood pressure.		alkaloids	
8.	Agarwood (Biak)	-	<i>Aquilaria malaccensis Lamk</i>	Used as a remedy for , hepatitis, asthma, liver and kidney inflammation (), an antibiotic for TB, rheumatism, tumours, a nerve stimulant, stomach ache, aphrodisiac, lung ailments, cancer, malaria and stomach ulcers.	12,958 µg/mL	Flavonoids and phenolic compounds	(Surjanto <i>et al.</i> , 2019)(13)
9.	Lasun wood (Papua New Guinea)	-	<i>Dysoxylum alliaceum</i>	As an anticancer, antioxidant and antibacterial agent.	8.65 µg/mL	Alkaloids, biflavonoids, sesquiterpenes , diterpenes, triterpenes, and steroids	(Nurcahyanti <i>et al.</i> , 2015)(14)
10.	Mantangan Leaves (Papua New Guinea)	Fresh Leaves	<i>Merremia peltata (L.) Merr</i>	Used to treat boils, as a compress for wounds, and for skin conditions.	47.41 µg/mL	Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, terpenoids/steroids and phenolic compounds	(Muhti'atul, Hanafi and Elya, 2021)(15)
11.	Pulai	Milkwood (all ethnic groups)	<i>(Alstonia scholaris L.)</i>	An infusion made from the bark or dried wood is drunk to treat fever and malaria. It is also used to treat stomach ache or diarrhoea, coughs, and to induce abortion	48 µg/mL	Phenolic compounds and flavonoids	(Thahira <i>et al.</i> , 2021)(16)
12.	Ketul or ajeran	Ajeran leaves	<i>(Bidens pilosa L.)</i>	Heals swelling, rheumatism, boils, and external wounds	62.03 µg/mL	Flavonoids and terpenoids	(Sariningsih <i>et al.</i> , 2016)(17)
13.	Taro	Taro. Wamona, Kom, Nomo, Uma, Warimu, Hè kéré, Sè kéré, Ifen, Yéfam	<i>(Colocasia esculenta L. Schott)</i>	Communities in the central highlands of Papua use the leaf stalks to treat pain, swelling and sprains	308 µg/mL	Phenolic compounds	(Nur-Hadirah <i>et al.</i> , 2021)(18)
14.	Ant nests	Ant nest	<i>(Myrmecodia spp.)</i>	Heals inflammation, relieves muscle pain, treats cancer and diabetes	566,087 µg/mL	Flavonoids, tannins, and polyphenolic compounds	(Moatar <i>et al.</i> , 2020)(19)
15.	Chinese	Chinese	<i>(Cassia</i>	Treats skin diseases,	9.96 µg/mL	Phenolic	(Bunya and

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	ketepeng	ketepeng, Kaskado leaves (used almost throughout Papua)	<i>alata</i> Linn.)	particularly scabies or kaskado caused by the <i>Sarcoptes scabiei</i> mite or fungal skin infections caused by <i>Tinea imbricate</i>		compounds and flavonoids	Lihan, 2022)(20)
16.	Bone-healing plants	Bone-setting plant	(<i>Euphorbia tirucalli</i> L.)	Used as a liniment for sprains or fractures and to treat snake and fish bites	13.6 µg/ml	Phenolic compounds	(Abdel-Aty <i>et al.</i> , 2019)(21)
17.	Rosella	Rosella	(<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L.)	Increases n, physical stamina and blood production	67.3 µg/mL	ic acid, phenols, anthocyanins and flavonoids	Inggrid <i>et al.</i> , 2018)(22)
18.	Black ginger	Forest ginger (Sentani)	(<i>Curcuma aeruginosa</i> Roxb.)	Increases appetite	15.42 ± 1.5 µg/ml	Phenolic compounds and flavonoids	(Zohmachhu ana <i>et al.</i> , 2022)(23)
19.	Cat's whiskers plant	Cat's whiskers leaves	(<i>Orthosiphon aristatus</i> Blume Miq.)	A decoction made with wungu leaves can be used as a drink to treat kidney stones	65.62513 µg/mL	Flavonoids	(Salasa <i>et al.</i> , 2021)(24)
20.	Takokak	Wild aubergine, Mini aubergine	(<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw.)	According to the people of Timika, it can be used as a natural substance to temporarily inhibit male fertility (sperm inactivation) for approximately 40 days after consumption (natural contraception)	85.58 µg/mL	Flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins	(Helilusiadini ngsih <i>et al.</i> , 2019)(25)
21.	Roda fruit	Kandarek (Biak tribe)	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Antidiabetic, antihypertensive, antidiuretic,	62.3 mg/L.	Serotonin alkaloid, plant steroid, alisarin, lysine, sodium, caprylic acid, arginine, proxeronine, anthraquinone, trace elements, phenylalanine, magnesium, terpenoids	(Ministry of Health, 2016)(26)
22.	Forest bitter gourd	Forest bitter gourd	<i>Momordica balsamina</i> Linn.	anti-inflammatory	127.95 µg/mL	alkaloids, steroids, phenolics and	(Awaladah <i>et al.</i> , 2017)(27)

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						flavonoids (Methanol extract)	
23.	African leaf	African leaf	<i>Vernonia amygdalina Del.</i>	cancer treatment, prevention of heart disease, lowering cholesterol, preventing stroke, regulating blood sugar, digestive disorders, and weight loss.	48.39 ppm	saponins, coumarins, phenolic acids, lignans, terpenes, luteolin and flavonoids	(Erwin <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Handjojo, 2018)(28)
24.	Pandemor	Pandemor (biak numfor)	<i>Phempis acidula.</i>	Swelling, toothache, boils	-	Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, triterpenoids	(Tarakanita <i>et al.</i> , 2019)(29)
25.	Abanik	Abanik (Lanny Jaya)	<i>Datura stramonium L. var.</i>	Runny nose, pain and fever	32.2 g/L	alkaloids, phytic acid, oxalate, tannin, terpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, phenols	(Sakadzo <i>et al.</i> , 2018)(30)
26.	Aka lambuang	Sea spinach (Timika)	<i>Merremia peltata (L.)</i>	The fresh stem, softened or crushed, is used for fresh wounds, burns and old wounds. The softened stem is also used for pain and swelling. Slices of the stem are used to stop bleeding from fresh wounds. Fresh leaves can be used to heal skin wounds when applied directly to the wound. The pounded stem is dissolved in water and drunk to cure whooping cough. The sap of the young shoots is used to treat eye inflammation. Small slices of the stem are heated over a flame and the hot vapour is blown onto the affected area	LC ₅₀ of "Aka Lambuang" leaf extract: 19.678 ppm; the hexane fraction yielded an LC ₅₀ value of 22.029 ppm; the ethyl acetate fraction yielded an LC ₅₀ value of 130.918 ppm	terpenoids, steroids, saponins and phenolics	(Alen <i>et al.</i> , 2016;(31) Honesty, 2012).(32)

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27.	Forest katuk	Forest katuk	<i>Breynia cernua</i>	treats breast cancer breast cancer and cervical cancer.	IC ₅₀ values are 246,841 ppm, 165.65 ppm, 562.57 ppm and 713.78 ppm	, flavonoids and quinones	(Khan <i>et al.</i> , 2008;(33) Dirgantara, 2018)(34)
28.	Jilat leaves	Jilat Leaf	<i>Villebrunear ubescens</i>	heals bruises	61.82 µm	alkaloids, tannins, saponins, quinones, and steroids with antibacterial activity, and cytotoxic properties (containing active compounds for anticancer use).	(Gunawan, 2018)(35)
29.	Sea grape (ambai)	Sea Grapes	<i>Caulerpa sp.</i>	Antifungal	1000 ppm	saponins and flavonoids	(Dimara <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Siregar, 1991)(36)
30.	Nelambo Suon (Yali tribe)		<i>Rubiaceae</i>	Antimalarial	IC ₅₀ values of 535.89 ppm at 29 minutes and 385.06 ppm at 59 minutes; the antioxidant test results indicate very weak activity.	alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, steroid saponins, terpenoids, quinones	(Christomo <i>et al.</i> , 2015)(37) (Oktolia <i>et al.</i> , 2017)(38)
31.	Nutmeg	Nutmeg	<i>Myristica fragrans Houtt</i>	Nutmeg is used in medicine as a carminative, astringent, narcotic, aphrodisiac, and to treat flatulence, nausea and vomiting.	1.016082 µg/mL	Nutmeg possesses antioxidant activity	(Phulsagar <i>et al.</i> , 2014;(39) Krishnamoorthy <i>et al.</i> , 2003;(40) Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2000)(41)
32.	Black Betel	Black Betel	<i>Piper betle var. nigra</i>	Empirical use of black betel leaves related to antioxidants involves the use of black betel leaves in the treatment of diabetes mellitus.	158.53 ppm	Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, steroids, triterpenoids and polyphenols	(Rija'i, 2015;(42) Backer and Bakhuizen van den Brink Jr, 1963)(43)
33.	Aru Root	Aru Root	<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i>	a plant used as a remedy for malaria by the	783.05; 374.93; 696.84 mg/L	alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins,	(Singh & Raghav,2012 (44);

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				Kanum tribe. Use of <i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i> , particularly the seeds, as a remedy is also practised by communities in Africa and India		tannins and triterpenoids	Assogbadjo <i>et al.</i> , 2011)(45)
34.	Water Spinach Flower	Water Spinach Flower	<i>Ipomoea carnea</i> Jack	This plant has potential anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antidiabetic, antimicrobial, wound-healing, immunomodulatory, cardiovascular, embryotoxic, antifungal, hepatoprotective, and inhibitory	12 ppm	flavonoids, saponins, polyphenols and alkaloids	(Sharma <i>et al.</i> , 2013)(46)
35.	Elephant Grass Root	<i>Imperata Cylindrica</i>	<i>Imperata cylindrica (L) Beauv.</i>	Communities in Southeast Sulawesi have been using elephant grass roots (<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>) as a remedy for hypertension.	0.32 mg/mL	Phenols	(Mensah MEE <i>et al.</i> , 2014)(47)
36.	Sidaguri	Sidaguri	<i>Sida rhombifolin</i> Linn.	The people of Timika use this plant to treat boils. The people of Dogiyai use this medicinal plant to treat diabetes mellitus (DM) by drinking a decoction of the leaves, stems and roots	4.26 µg/ml	Flavonoids, tannins and saponins	
37.	Gambir	Agya (Kanum people) and Ake (Marori and Marind people)	<i>Uncaria gambir (Hunt) Roxb.</i>	Used as a remedy for burns, headaches, diarrhoea, dysentery, as a mouthwash, for mouth ulcers and for skin ailments.	6.4 µg/mL	Flavonoids, catechins and tannins	

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38.	African leaf	African leaves	<i>vernonia Amygdalina Del.</i>	This African plant is a herbal remedy first used in traditional Congolese medicine and is widely used in the treatment of malaria.	4.34 µg/mL	contains various secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, saponins, tannins, and glycosides	(Omoregie, 2011)(48)
39.	Matoa	Hatar (Trimuris, Mamberamo)	<i>Pometia pinnata</i> J.R. Foster & J.G Foster	A decoction of the leaves and bark can be used to treat and festering wounds. A hot water infusion of the leaves is used to treat dysentery.	4 µg/mL (ethanol extract of matoa bark) 9 µg/mL (ethyl acetate extract of matoa bark) 5 µg/mL (chloroform extract of matoa bark) 25 µg/mL (n-hexane extract of matoa bark)	Phenolic compounds (flavonoids)	(Hasan <i>et al.</i> , 2022)(49)
40.	Zodia plant	<i>Evodia suaveolens</i> Sceff	<i>Evodia suaveolens</i>	used to repel mosquitoes	170 µg/mL (methanol extract of Zodia plant leaves)	secondary metabolites belonging to the alkaloid, flavonoid, and tannin groups	(Ngibad and Lilla, 2019)(50)
41.	Bintangur	Tembuy (Maribu) Bintangur (Papua)	<i>Callophylum inophyllum</i> L.	Dried bintangur leaves are burned, and inhaling the smoke can alleviate vertigo and migraines	65.49 µg/mL (Ethanol extract fraction)	Flavonoid compounds	(Faisal <i>et al.</i> , 2022)(51)
42.	Waru leaves	Wenata (Tamakuri, Waropen), Wakati (Merauke)	<i>Hibiscus tiliaceus</i>	As a remedy for bruises	58,564 ± 1,412 µg/mL (methanol extract of waru leaves)	Phenolic Compounds	(Putri <i>et al.</i> , 2021)(52)
43.	Forest Katuk	Forest Katuk	<i>Phyllanthus</i> sp. Var.	The leaves are used to treat breast cancer, uterine cancer and cysts	80.81 µg/mL (methanol extract of	Flavonoid compounds	(Zuhra <i>et al.</i> , 2008)(53)

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	Leaves		Papua		katuk leaves)		
44.	Castor	Yole (Lemongrass), Sot-Sot (Maribu) Becai (Sobey)	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Slightly young leaves to reduce fever. The tip of the stem for toothache	7.8 µg/mL (ethyl acetate extract of castor oil plant leaves) 7.2 µg/mL (ethyl acetate fraction of <i>Jatropha curcas</i> twigs)	flavonoid and polyphenol groups	(Setyaningsih <i>et al.</i> , 2014)(54)
45.	Beluntas Sarmi	Beluntas	<i>Pluchea indica</i> (L.) Less	Used to prevent <i>postpartum</i> white blood cell infection	107 µg/mL (chloroform extract of beluntas leaves)	Phenolic compounds	(Nafisah and Tukiran, 2017)(55)
46.	Purple leaf	Blood leaf, red leaf	<i>Graptophyllum pictum</i> (L.) Griff	Used as a blood-building agent and for treating diarrhoea	125.09 µg/mL. (Purple leaf infusion)	Phenolic Compounds (Anthocyanins)	(Salim, 2018)(56)
47.	Areca Nut	Daud (Maribu), Afef-ou (Sereh), Auk (Waropen), Ropum (Nansfori)	<i>Areca catechu</i> L.	Used as a remedy for worms and toothache, and as a tooth strengthener	3.5 µg/ml (ethanol extract of areca nut)	Flavonoid Compounds	(Cahyanto, 2018)(57)
48.	Sambiloto	Sambiloto	<i>Adrographis paniculata</i> (Burm. f) Wall. ex Nees	Used to treat malaria	16,634 µg/mL (ethanol extract of sambiloto root)	Phenolic compounds (flavonoids)	(Utami 2021)(58)
49.	Forest pandan	Woromo	<i>(Pandanus julianettii martelli)</i>	The forest coconut pandan plant is used by the community for various daily purposes, ranging from food flavouring and medicine to religious ceremonies.	45.83 µg/mL	Methanol and Tocopherols	(Zebua and Purnamasari, 2017)(59)
50.	White wood	Huek	<i>(Eucalyptus alba)</i>	The huek fruit is used to treat liver disease and boost the immune system.	10,402 µg/mL	Methanol	(Darmakusuma <i>et al.</i> , 2019)(60)
51.	Nutmeg	Hanggi	<i>(Myristica</i>	Nutmeg is used by	100.52	Alkaloids and	(Sari <i>et al.</i> ,

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			<i>fragrans Houtt)</i>	local people to treat diarrhoea and as an antibacterial agent.	µg/mL	flavonoids	2022)(61)
52.	Mahkota dewa	Mahkota dewa	<i>(Phaleria macrocarpa)</i>	Mahkota dewa is used as a medicinal plant for its antibacterial and antiviral properties, as well as to reduce blood sugar levels.	127.983 µg/mL	Flavonoids, saponins, polyphenols and alkaloids	(Kurang & Malaipada, 2021)(62)
53.	Pitcher plant	Pitcher plant	<i>(Nepenthes rafflesiana Jack)</i>	The pitcher plant is used in traditional medicine as eye drops, for burns, coughs, fever, hypertension, jaundice, incontinence, kidney stones, tenderness, as a wound cleanser, and to prevent or treat bedwetting in children.	38.83 µg/mL	Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and tannins	(Putri <i>et al.</i> , 2022)(63)
54.	Soursop	Soursop	<i>(Annona muricata, Linn)</i>	Soursop is used by local people to treat malaria using its leaves.	192.13 µg/mL	flavonoids, terpenoids, and tannins	(Alim <i>et al.</i> , 2021)(64)
55.	Yellow root	Yellow root	<i>(Arcangelisi a flava)</i>	Yellow root is used to treat various conditions such as ringworm, scabies, tinea, malaria, fever, and certain bacterial infections.	136.81 µg/mL	Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and polyphenols,	(Suratno <i>et al.</i> , 2019)(65)
56.	Noni	Noni	<i>(Morinda citrifolia L)</i>	Among local communities, noni is used as a remedy for stomach ache.	4.14 µg/mL (in leaf extract); 5.78 µg/mL (in fruit pulp extract); 0.68 µg/mL (in seed extract)	Polyphenols, alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, and phenols.	(Qulub <i>et al.</i> , 2018)(66)
57.	-sarai palm	Sarai	<i>(Caryota mitis)</i>	The sarai palm can be used as an ornamental plant, and its n starch can be extracted to produce sago, as well as serving as a traditional medicinal ingredient.	62.5 µg/mL	Flavonoids	(Abdelhaki <i>et al.</i> , 2017)(67)
58.	Girang	Girang	<i>(Leea</i>	Girang roots are	1.62 µg/mL	Flavonoids,	(Kartikasari,

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			<i>indica</i>)	useful as a remedy for fungal infections, malaria and stomach ache; the flowers can be used to treat boils; the leaves are useful for treating palpitations, dizziness, sprains and postnatal care; the wood is useful for treating wounds, and the bark can be used as an antidote to snake venom.		saponins, tannins, and polyphenols	2015)(68)
59.	Dollu (Lanny or central highlands)	Dollu	<i>Dodonaea viscosa (L.) Jacq</i>	Dollu leaves are heated over a flame or embers until they become oily () and are then applied or pressed onto a fresh wound to stop the bleeding and prevent infection, as well as accelerate wound healing	The highest scavenging activity in the flower and leaf parts was exhibited by WA extracts with an IC ₅₀ of 116.7 mg/mL and 47.99 mg/mL respectively	Polyphenols, oxygenated nor-diterpenes and diterpenes, alizarin, pinocembrin, penduletin, viscosol, isokaempferol and kaempferol-trimethyl ether	(Malik <i>et al.</i> , 2022)(69)
60.	Pegagang, horse's foot (Kampung Bomela, Wamena)	Omeya	<i>Centella asiatica (L.) Urban</i>	For reducing fever or heat , epilepsy.	98.6 ± 1.6 µg/mL	Kaempferol, quercetin, and rutin. Chemical Brahmoside, centelosa, madecassoside, brahmi acid, carotenoids, several minerals and possesses antimicrobial activity, acts as a diuretic, and is used for typhoid and influenza.	(Buranasudja <i>et al.</i> , 2021) (70)
61.	Sedge (Found almost throughout the Papua region)	omgas	<i>Imperata cylindrica (L.) Beauv</i>	Heals wounds, fever, headache, - bacterial, anti-inflammatory	192.07 ± 0.78 µg/mL)	lignin, holocellulose, alpha-cellulose, pentosan/hemicellulose,	(Z.R. Razafindrakoto <i>et al.</i> , 2021)(71)

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						arundoin, fernenol, isoarborinol, cylindrin, cylindol A, simiarenol, campesterol, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, scopoletin, scopolin, p-hydroxybenzaldehyde, catechol, chlorogenic acid, isochlorogenic acid, p-coumaric acid, neochlorogenic acid, acetic acid, oxalic acid, d-malic acid, citric acid, potassium (0.75% of dry weight), significant amounts of calcium, 5-hydroxytryptamine and flavonoids	
62.	Gedi leaves (Jayapura, Merauke, Jayawijaya)	swotpun	<i>Abelmoschus manihot (L.)</i>	treats kidney pain, lowers cholesterol, diarrhoea and stomach ulcers, toothache	233 bpj	phenolic compounds, flavonoids, steroids, alkaloids and tannins,	(Manalu <i>et al.</i> , 2022) (72)
63.	Kemunting (Dani tribe)		<i>Rhodomyrtus tomentosa</i>	Treats diarrhoea, dysentery, inflammation, fever	Ethanol extract of young leaves 14.67 ppm, methanol extract of mature leaves 19.86 ppm	Tannins, flavonoids, phenols, amino acids, quinones, steroids.	(Kuntorini <i>et al.</i> , 2019) (73)
64.	Guava leaves (Throughout Papua)	giawas	<i>Psidium guajava L.</i>	Inflammation, diarrhoea, cholera	3.55 mg/L	flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, anthocyanins,	(Sekarsari <i>et al.</i> , 2019) (74)

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						carotenoids, essential oils, and phenols.	
65.	Porcupine flower (Dani tribe, Jayawijaya)	anikukuh	<i>Barleria prionitis</i>	Treats wounds	60.22 µg/mL	Alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols,	(Shukla, 2019) (75)
66.	Sugar cane (Jayawijaya, Merauke, Nabire, Sarmi)	yagar	<i>Saccharum officinarum L</i>	For physical stamina	72.65 ppm	Flavonoids, gallic acid	(Priyanto & Islamiyati, 2018) (76)
67.	Sambaing getih (Dani tribe, Jayawijaya)	Irugum	<i>Hemigraphis colorata Hall</i>	Internal heat, cough	24.15 ppm	Flavonoids, polyphenols, and tannins	(Dewi <i>et al.</i> , 2023) (77)
68.	Turmeric (Throughout Papua)	podu	<i>Curcuma longa L.</i>	digestive disorders, blood purifier, heart tonic, stomach tonic, diuretic	25.42 µg/mL	curcumin, demethoxycurcumin and bisdemethoxy curcumin	(Quirós-Fallas <i>et al.</i> , 2022) (78)
69.	Red Fruit (Tengah, Wamena)	tawi	<i>Pandanus conoideus Lamk</i>	fruit oil Red is used as cooking oil and a base ingredient for medicines. Pieces of the red fruit, boiled together with sweet potato leaves, are used as pig feed. The leaves of the red fruit have not yet been utilised effectively, although it is known to be suitable for weaving.	37.69 µg/mL	carotenoids, tocopherols, beta-carotene, α-tocopherol, and fatty acids such as oleic acid, linoleic acid, linolenic acid, and decanoic acid.	(Susanti, Rohman and Setyaningsi, 2022 ; Wawo, Lestari and Setyowati, 2019) (79) ;(80)
70.	Papuan Grapes (Kayari (Yapen), Selre (Depapre, Sentani), Jayapura)	Arrayan	<i>Sararanga sinousa Hemsley</i>	As a mineral and vitamin supplement.	12.23 µg/mL	Syringic acid, isovanillic acid (hydroxybenzoic acid group), chlorogenic acid, 2-hydroxycinnamic acid, sinapic acid, caffeic acid, and ferulic acid (hydroxycinnamic acid group).	(Purnamasari, Lunga and Widjanarko, 2020) (81)

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the distribution of Papua's endemic plants with antioxidant potential, 32 regions across Papua were identified, namely Sorong and Manokwari (masoyi); Tambrau (kebar grass); Nabire (masoyi and sugarcane); Lani (red sugarcane); Nansfori (areca nut); Biak Numfor (masoyi and pandemor); Tamakuri (waru leaves); Trimuris (matoa); Mamberamo (matoa); Waropen (masoyi, waru leaves, areca nuts); Paniai (ant nests); Timika (Takokak, Aka lambuang, sidaguri); Sarmi (meniran, beluntas, sugarcane); Maribu (bintangur, castor oil plant, areca nuts); Depapre (Papuan grapes); Sereh (castor oil plant, areca nut); Tolikara, Puncak Jaya, Bupul and Wasur (ant nests); Wamena (Besaran, Pegagang, horse's foot); Lanny Jaya (Abanik, Dollu); Jayawijaya (Gedi leaves, porcupine flower, sugarcane, sambaing getih); Bomela (pegagang, horse's foot); Jayapura (lobi-lobi, masoyi, gedi leaves, Papua grapes); Keerom (milkwood, Chinese ketepeng); Merauke (masoyi, waru leaves, gedi leaves, sugarcane); PNG (pekak, lasun wood, mantangan leaves). Furthermore, based on a literature review of the empirical use of endemic Papuan plants with antioxidant potential, 70 plants were identified, with all parts of the plant—leaves, stems and roots—being utilised.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors sincerely acknowledge all parties for their support, guidance, and assistance in the completion of this research.

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